

Anton Kurnia's Novel *Majnun*: The Dynamics of Social Criticism in the New Order Era

Natasya Aulia Re Elirina ✉

*Indonesian Language and Literature Education, Teacher Training and Education,
University of Muhammadiyah Purwokerto, Indonesia*

Onok Yayang Pamungkas

*Indonesian Language and Literature Education, Teacher Training and Education,
University of Muhammadiyah Purwokerto, Indonesia*

Abstract

This research aims to reveal the social problems criticized in the novel *Majnun* by Anton Kurnia and explain the relevance of social criticism in the novel *Majnun* by Anton Kurnia in daily life. This research uses a hermeneutic method. The data collection techniques carried out by the author are reading, recording and classifying techniques according to categories. The data analysis technique is that the author conducts in-depth literacy so that he is able to produce research results. The results of the study show that in the novel *Majnun* by Anton Kurnia there are social problems that occur, these problems include political/government problems, economic, social, cultural, religious, gender inequality, morality and family disorganization. These problems are a reflection of life during the New Era. The novel provides an overview or glimpse of the social situation at that time, there were many social events that could be criticized. In the novel *Majnun* by Anton Kurnia, it highlights many things that are relevant to today's life. The problems raised in the novel are still very relevant to life today. Relevant things such as bribery and embezzlement are still there, the economic gap in Indonesia is still very high, human morals and behavior at will, the underdevelopment of women who are considered weak by men, the fading of traditional culture, a person's distrust of religion, the existence of ethnic and religious discrimination in Indonesia, environmental damage caused by global warming and industrial activities and the amount of violence against children who are caused by parental pressure. The implications of social criticism in the novel *Majnun* by Anton Kurnia are awareness of the importance of justice, respect for differences, support freedom of speech, demand transparency from political parties and provide empathy to victims of injustice.

Keywords: *novel Majnun, Anton Kurnia, social criticism, New Order Era, hermeneutics.*

Suggested citation: Re Elirina, N.A., & Pamungkas, O.Y. (2025). Anton Kurnia's Novel *Majnun*: The Dynamics of Social Criticism in the New Order Era. *European Journal of Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences*, 2(3), 44-57. DOI: 10.59324/ejahss.2025.2(3).04

Introduction

Social problems are a phenomenon that is always present in the dynamics of people's lives, both on a local, national, and global scale. In general, social problems can be interpreted as conditions or behaviors that are considered detrimental, disturbing the balance, or causing injustice in society. Social problems (social problems) are problems that arise in society, are social in nature and are closely related to social values and social institutions (Soerjano, 2006). Social problems occur because there is a striking difference between the values in a society and the real conditions of life. A social problem is actually the result of social interaction between individuals, between individuals and groups or between a group and another

This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/). The license permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, on the condition that users give exact credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons license, and indicate if they made any changes.

group (Maryati & Suryawati, 2016). A new problem can be said to be a social problem if the condition is felt by many people. If there is a clash between the existing elements, it will cause a disturbance of social relations such as social problems that occur in society (Augustine, 2017; Juda, 2011). These issues are often complex, interrelated, and influenced by a variety of factors, such as economic, political, cultural, and educational. Social problems that occur today such as social inequality, economic inequality, gender inequality, government/politics, religion, morals, culture, environment and family disorganization. These social problems are different from other problems in society because they are closely related to social values and social institutions (Tutesa & Wisman, 2020) Social problems are also often a reflection of the failure of existing systems in society. Injustice in the distribution of resources, policies that do not favor the small people, or a deep-rooted patriarchal culture can worsen social conditions. Therefore, understanding social problems is not just about looking at the symptoms that appear on the surface, but also exploring the root of the underlying problem.

Social problems in the context of social inequality are still often seen, for example in education, health and economic welfare. Social inequality has an impact on new problems, namely economic inequality, economic inequality occurs due to a lack of jobs. Increasingly narrow employment opportunities will create economic inequality. Employment is now also dominated by men. This triggers a new social problem, namely gender inequality, women who are always considered to be below men. In government/politics, there are often social problems that occur within the scope of government but have an impact on the society under it. Money laundering and bribery activities are commonplace, but they are actually a big social problem. One of the reasons why money politics is rampant is when the role of political parties is dwarfed, so that the institution of political parties is weakened. Then the problem of the implementation of an open proportional system which has an impact on the weakening of party institutions then boils down to behavior *money politic* is closely related to this (Revan et al., 2022). The social problem of religion is always connected with the social and moral problem, the relationship between the two because religion is the source of morality. Some parties also blame religion for justifying morally wrong actions, for example, in the name of religion for corruption in the name of donations for the construction of places of worship. Social and environmental issues are also closely related. Many socio-cultural problems provide bad effects for the environment. Social criticism of the environment occurs due to a surge in population, air and water pollution due to waste, deforestation and burning of forests for land clearing, agriculture, fisheries, mining, and unsustainable development, a consumerist lifestyle, and the birth of large corporations that exploit natural resources are some of the human activities that cause environmental damage (Laksonia & Wijaksono, 2022). The problem of family disorganization is also in the spotlight, it occurs because of the disharmony of family members which has a great negative impact. Family disorganization is the division of the family as a unit because its members fail to fulfill their obligations in accordance with their social roles (Mustafidah et al., 2022). Based on existing social problems, writers use problems as a medium to express their anxiety through a literary work.

For this reason, literature is a medium that is not only a place to record something but literature is also used to pour out all the contents of thoughts and literature can also be used to criticize the social reality that exists around it. Literature can be expressed into a work, the work is called a literary work. Literature as a reflection of the social life of the community serves to reflect the social life of the community into literary works. In the sense that literary works reflect what the author's views are towards the surrounding community (Humaira & Satriani, 2024). Literary works express the author's ideas related to the essence and values of life which include human, social, cultural, moral, political, gender, educational, and divine or religiosity aspects. Literary works are an individual "product" that cannot be separated from the influence of materialist foundations (Magnis & Suseno, 2016). In the development of literary works, literature is often used as a reflection of the dynamics of people's lives. Literature presents issues that are relevant to people's lives today. Through literary works, the author expresses the problems of life that the author feels and that are found in his social environment. Many literary works explore social issues more, one of which is in novels.

The exploration of social problems in literature, especially in novel literary works, is to understand how social phenomena, conflicts, and the dynamics of human life are expressed through literary narratives.

Novels as a form of literary work are often a reflection of the reality of society, both explicitly and implicitly. In a novel the author expresses himself through writing, in a novel the author can make a story using events, characters and places imaginatively. One of the novels that raises complex social issues is the novel *Majnun* by Anton Kurnia. Anton Kurnia's novel *Majnun* not only offers a profound story of love and madness, but also highlights various social issues relevant to life. In the novel *Majnun* by Anton Kurnia, researchers can explore social problems, analyze, and interpret various social issues raised by the author and related to the reality of today's life. Through the approach of literary sociology, the researcher uncovers the reciprocal relationship between literary texts and the social context in which the work was created. In addition, this research also aims to see how social, cultural, political, economic, and moral values are presented in novels, as well as how these literary works can be a tool for social criticism or reflection on the conditions of society in a certain period. Thus, this research not only provides an in-depth understanding of the literary works themselves, but also provides insight into the complexity of social problems faced by humans, as well as offering a new perspective in viewing social reality through a literary lens.

For this reason, the relationship of social reality in the novel *Majnun* by Anton Kurnia is important to study because in the novel *Majnun* there are many social problems that reflect life at that time. Social reality in the form of literature is in the form of representation or depiction of social phenomena, so literature is a reflection of social reality. The relationship between *Majnun's* novel and social reality is a critique of social injustice, in the novel it tells about characters who experience oppression and injustice. This novel focuses more on social problems than on political issues. In this novel, it tells about power will benefit one party and the other will suffer oppression. Nowadays, many people use their power for personal matters without looking at others. The abuse of power will not be separated from acts of corruption or embezzlement of funds, at this time many people are embezzling funds for personal gain. In addition, the relationship of social reality in *Majnun's* novel is also about acts of discrimination, where small groups are considered different and treated unfairly. It is very clear that if a group will be isolated and considered different, it will create injustice in daily treatment. The relationship between social reality in the novel is the importance of education and critical awareness in fighting injustice. The same is true of the reality where educated people tend to be more critical and able to resist oppression, while less educated people will be submissive and just silent. This novel provides an overview of the social reality that occurred during the New Era government, in *Majnun's* novel describes how the characters face repression and pressure when trying to voice the truth or fight injustice.

Thus, the purpose of this research is to explore the social dynamics/criticism in the novel *Majnun* by Anton Kurnia, namely to understand the social dynamics/criticism that occurred in the novel *Majnun* during the New Era, which includes injustice, social inequality, corruption and discrimination. In addition, another purpose is to show that literature can be a means to criticize society, because at that time people did not dare to express social unrest so they used literature as a means to criticize it. In addition, the purpose of this research is to study social problems that exist in life, social problems that are considered simple can actually become a branch of new social problems. This research also aims to explore in depth the social criticism and dynamics raised in *Majnun's* novel, as well as relate it to the historical context and its relevance to today's social life. So that through this analysis, it is hoped that readers will get a calm picture of social dynamics during the New Era, as well as literature functioning as a portrait of social life at that time.

Materials and Methods

This research uses the hermeneutic method. The term hermenetics comes from the Greek word namely *Hermeneuein* which is interpreted as "interpret" (Susanto, 2016). Hermeneutics is not just an activity related to language, but also as an act of interpretation and interpretation (Ricoeur, 1981). The object used in this study is a sentence that contains social criticism in the novel *Majnun* by Anton Kurnia. Meanwhile, the subject of this study is what is the background for the occurrence of social criticism. The data in this study is in the form of lingual such as sentences, paragraphs and discourses that contain social criticism

in the novel *Majnun* by Anton Kurnia. The data source used by the author in conducting this research is Novel *Majnun* by Anton Kurnia. The data collection techniques carried out by the author are reading, recording and classifying techniques according to categories. The data analysis technique is that the author conducts in-depth literacy so that he is able to produce research results. The steps used in this study are reading the manuscript of the novel *Majnun* by Anton Kurnia, by reading in detail, the author can classify data in accordance with the social problems that are criticized. After classifying, it is followed by encoding the data with the format (M/D0.../page...), which means "M" is the title code of the novel *Majnun*, "D0" is the numerical data and "p" is the data excerpt page in the novel *Majnun*. After coding the data, the author interprets the data that has been found with social reality and relevance to daily life and finally the researcher makes a conclusion from the findings.

Results

Social criticism is an analysis or response to social problems that occur in society. Social criticism in a literary work can be used to express social inequality and injustice in society. The analysis of social criticism in the novel *Majnun* by Anton Kurnia using a literary sociology review found nine (9) aspects of life that were criticized, namely:

Socio-Political/Government Criticism

Social problems in the field of government/politics are related to people or groups who have power in a region with certain institutions. Social problems in the field of government/politics are not far from the scope of government authority, applicable policies and matters that fall into the realm of government/politics. In the novel *Majnun* by Anton Kurnia, there is a lot of social criticism about government/political issues. Based on this, table 1 describes social criticism related to government/politics in the novel *Majnun* by Anton Kurnia.

Table 1. Social Criticism of Government/Politics in the Novel *Majnun* by Anton Kurnia

Quotation	Criticized aspects	Data code
<i>"The action protested against the low wages set by the colonial and demanded a salary increase"</i>	Granting rights incompletely	M/D01/P/p. 45
<i>"Yusuf is willing to risk his life by joining the pro-democracy movement against the repressive New Order regime. During that time, many activists were disappeared, kidnapped, tortured, and killed by the authorities."</i>	The ruling apparatus that legalizes all means for the smooth running of the plan	M/D02/P/p. 71
<i>In the early hours of October 1, 1965, there was a crept coup against President Soekarno and the legitimate Indonesian government."</i>	Coup or attempted power grab carried out illegally	M/D03/P/p. 85
<i>"Hundreds of thousands of other people were imprisoned without trial and some were exiled to Buru Island for up to a dozen years as political prisoners"</i>	Sentenced without trial	M/D04/P/p. 85-86
<i>"The election of Suharto as President of the Republic of Indonesia for the third time in 1978 caused protests among students. There has been a growing awareness that the government is in power with an authoritarian. In addition, corruption of state officials is increasingly rampant"</i>	Authoritarian government and rampant corruption	M/D05/P/p. 87
<i>It is common knowledge that petty criminals are often used by the official authorities as accomplices in dirty work, including political terror against dissidents."</i>	Official officials who involve others in dirty work	M/D06/P/p. 88
<i>"The Emperor's father is also a state official like my father. But, the Emperor said, his father was a corrupt official. There is a bribe of money. The Emperor's family moved from Medan to Jakarta when he was a teenager"</i>	Corruption and bribery	M/D07/P/p. 97
<i>"Meanwhile, the political elite is constantly strategizing to maintain power on behalf of the people who are increasingly squeezed by the pressures of daily life"</i>	Defending power on behalf of the people	M/D08/P/p. 165-166

<i>"Veronica, who is now a well-known women's activist, but failed to become a minister because she lost her connection"</i>	Connections in a government or the presence of insider help	M/D09/P/p. 166
<i>"Ronny was a party official, but was arrested by the KPK for a bribery case"</i>	Bribery cases	M/D10/P/p166
<i>"Majnun is like a state that is arbitrary towards its people who are helpless when they are oppressed and brutally killed just for demanding their rights"</i>	Arbitrary against the people	M/D11/P/p186

Information: M: *Majnun*; D: *Data*; P: *Politics*; Pp: *Yard*

In the novel *Majnun* by Anton Kurnia, there are 11 (eleven) data that show that in the novel there are many social problems in the government/political aspect. In today's life there are many of the same problems, the relevance in today's life of political/government criticism is very clear, according to the novel that a high-ranking person or person with a higher position will use the position to act arbitrarily. In *Majnun's* novel, there is a social criticism about the provision of wages that are not complete. In daily life, many government officials give incomplete wages to their workers, while the workers have given as much energy as possible. In the novel, it is explained that the rulers commit embezzlement or corruption, this is already seen as commonplace in Indonesia. Many state officials use state money for personal gain and legitimize all means to maintain their position in government. In addition to corruption, bribery activities are also rampant in Indonesia. Many people want a position by using money or bribes to be able to occupy that position.

Socio-Economic Criticism

Social problems in the economic field are very easy to see, the existence of economic disparities is the main factor in this social criticism. This criticism aims to expose injustice, inequality, and problems arising from economic practices. In the novel *Majnun* by Anton Kurnia, there is a lot of social criticism about economic problems. Based on this, table 2 describes social criticism related to economics in the novel *Majnun* by Anton Kurnia

Table 2. Socio-Economic Criticism in the Novel *Majnun* by Anton Kurnia

Quotation	Criticized aspects	Data code
<i>"Since raising the slave from Bali, his rank has risen quickly and his wealth has multiplied"</i>	Considering the poor as commoners	M/D11/E/p. 145
<i>"The motive is disgust at seeing crazy development and industrial exploitation"</i>	Industrial exploitation	M/D12/E/p. 170
<i>"According to him, his victims are the bastards of the Industrial Revolution agents whom he blames for all the crimes and destruction on earth, including capitalism, the "slavery" of man by corporations, economic inequality, and global warming."</i>	Capitalism	M/D13/E/p. 170-171

Information: M: *Majnun*; D: *Data*; P: *Politics*; Pp: *Yard*

In the novel *Majnun* by Anton Kurnia, there are social problems in the economic field, there is an economic gap, this happens because of economic practices. One of the relevance in daily life of socio-economic criticism is the existence of economic inequality that is clearly visible. The lowly or the poor were considered slaves by the richer people. This happens a lot nowadays, rich people think that poor people are weak people and have nothing. In addition, many people carry out industrial exploitation actions, where companies or individuals take advantage of resources, labor and the surrounding environment. The socio-economic criticism in the novel discusses the economics of capitalism where humans are enslaved to carry out economic activities.

Social Moral Criticism

Social problems in the moral field are life problems that we often encounter in our daily lives. Social moral criticism aims to identify injustices, inequality, or behaviors that are perceived as detrimental or

inconsistent with ethical and moral principles that are believed. Based on this, table 3 describes social criticism related to morality in the novel *Majnun* by Anton Kurnia.

Table 3. Social and Moral Criticism in the Novel *Majnun* by Anton Kurnia

Quotation	Criticized aspects	Data code
"Moreover, humans tend to be pretentious, arrogant and stubborn"	Sok smart, arrogant and stubborn	M/D14/MB/p. 139
"The greedy Peranggi people are so thirsty to expand their power in the archipelago in order to gain maximum profits"	A greedy person for a great profit	M/D15/MB/p. 141
"Life is not always fair and humans can be very cruel and cunning towards others"	Cruel and cunning human nature	M/D16/MB/p. 148

Information: M: *Majnun*; D: *Data*; P: *Politics*; Pp: *Yard*

In the novel *Majnun* by Anton Kurnia, there are prominent social and moral problems. A person's morality can be seen from how the person's attitude and behavior are. These social problems often occur in today's life, social and moral criticism can be clearly seen in the surrounding environment. In accordance with the analysis carried out, the novel tells a character who is stubborn, arrogant, greedy, cruel and cunning. In daily life, many people are also arrogant about what they have, in addition to being arrogant, there is also human greed. Nowadays, many people are greedy to get as much luck as possible, it is this trait that the author criticizes. In addition, human nature is also cruel and cunning, people can commit cruelty to anyone if they don't get what they want from others. Nowadays, many people commit acts of cruelty to fellow human beings because the person is hurt. Nowadays there are also many people who are cunning towards their neighbors, they do not care about others and are only selfish.

Social Criticism of Gender

Social problems in the field of gender include various forms of injustice, inequality, and discrimination experienced by individuals or groups based on gender. Gender inequality can be in various fields or various aspects, for example in the fields of education, employment, injustice in the political and legal systems, health and reproductive rights issues and many others. Based on this, table 4 describes the social criticism related to gender in the novel *Majnun* by Anton Kurnia.

Table 4. Social Criticism of Gender in the Novel *Majnun* by Anton Kurnia

Quotation	Criticized aspects	Data code
"Men in front, women in the back, because in our tradition women are always behind men"	Women are always behind men	M/D17/G/p. 8
"In our custom, naming and naming are not women's business. They can only get pregnant and give birth"	Considering that women can only get pregnant and give birth	M/D18/G/p. 9-10
"During the Japanese occupation, because of the difficulties of life, Sarinem became Kenji's mistress"	Women with economic difficulties end up becoming mistresses	M/D19/G/p. 84

Information: M: *Majnun*; D: *Data*; P: *Politics*; Pp: *Yard*

In the novel *Majnun* by Anton Kurnia, there is a social problem of gender inequality, in the novel it tells about gender inequality. This is very prominent, because women are considered to always be below men. The relevance of these problems in today's life is one of them, namely a woman who must always be below men, but in reality a woman can also be equal and equal to men. In this novel, it is explained that the position of a woman is clearly far below that of men, women are only allowed to get pregnant and give birth and do not have the right to take part in giving names. Nowadays there are still many people who think that women do not need to take part in giving names to the babies they have conceived. In

addition, women are also considered to always be behind men, in daily life many women who can exceed men are considered incapable because of gender differences.

Socio-Cultural Criticism

Cultural or cultural problems are problems that include existing cultures, this social criticism includes cultural practices, norms, and values that are considered problematic or unfair. This criticism is often aimed at exposing injustices and pushing for social change. Based on this, table 5 describes social criticism related to culture in the novel *Majnun* by Anton Kurnia.

Table 5. Socio-Cultural Criticism in the Novel *Majnun* by Anton Kurnia

Quotation	Criticized aspects	Data code
"As someone who was raised by parents who hold the traditions of ancestral heritage, since childhood I have been exposed to all traditional rituals. However, as a rational human, I feel objected to strange things that are irrelevant to me."	Forgetting about traditional culture	M/D20/SB/p. 21

Information: M: *Majnun*; D: *Data*; P: *Politics*; Pp: *Yard*

In the novel *Majnun* by Anton Kurnia, there is a cultural problem, this is the fading of traditional cultural values. The relevance of everyday life of socio-cultural criticism is the loss of traditional culture. Nowadays, many people have abandoned traditional culture that is believed for generations, this happens because of modernization. For example, the loss of traditional culture, namely traditional games, in ancient times traditional games such as playing congkak, gobak sodor and other toys became the daily activities of young children but now they have begun to fade and even disappeared because today's children tend to choose to play *smartphones* instead of playing traditional toys.

Religious Social Criticism

Social issues and social criticism in the context of religion are topics that are often debated. Religion, as a system of beliefs and values, is often expected to be a moral guide for society. However, religion can also be a source of social problems or a target of social criticism. Based on this, table 6 describes social criticism related to religion in the novel *Majnun* by Anton Kurnia.

Table 6. Socio-Religious Criticism in the Novel *Majnun* by Anton Kurnia

Quotation	Criticized aspects	Data code
"I accept that god exists as <i>Causa Prims</i> but I don't believe in religion"	Doubting things about religion	M/D21/A/p. 23

Information: M: *Majnun*; D: *Data*; P: *Politics*; Pp: *Yard*

The results of the research in the novel *Majnun* by Anton Kurnia explain that there are social problems related to religion. The problem is related to a person's disbelief in God, the problem is criticized because the person is considered to have no faith in God. The relevance in daily life of religious social criticism is the fading of religious science and religious teachings. In the novel, there is a socio-religious criticism that discusses doubting religion. In daily life, many people also doubt religion, for whom religion is not very important. People who do not believe in religion usually have their own beliefs that are far different from the religious teachings that exist in Indonesia.

Social Criticism of Humanity

Social criticism of humanity discusses inequality of human rights (HAM), human dignity and human welfare, but in life it can be seen that there are many things that need to be criticized, for example in the

gap or discrimination in an ethnicity, group or religion. Based on this, table 7 describes social criticism related to humanity in the novel *Majnun* by Anton Kurnia.

Table 7. Social Criticism of Humanity in the Novel *Majnun* by Anton Kurnia

Quotation	Criticized aspects	Data code
<i>"At that time, hundreds of ethnic Chinese were looted, raped and killed arbitrarily"</i>	Ethnically discriminated against	M/D22/K/p. 95
<i>"Ethnic and religious differences are a cause for fighting and competing to kill"</i>	Ethnic and religious discrimination	M/D23/K/p. 165

Information: M: *Majnun*; D: *Data*; P: *Politics*; Pp: *Yard*

The results of the research from the novel *Majnun* by Anton Kurnia found that in that era there were social problems related to humanity. These problems are related to discrimination or differentiation of a different ethnicity or group. One of the relevance of daily life to social criticism of humanity is the existence of ethnic and religious discrimination. In Indonesia, there is still clearly visible discriminatory behavior. Ethnic or ethnic discrimination is also very visible, for example, discrimination against Papuans and other ethnic people who are considered different from others. This discrimination sometimes triggers disputes between human groups. In addition, religious discrimination also occurs because other religious minorities are small so that they are considered to be different small groups. Even though in reality it will not differentiate between one and the other.

Social Criticism of the Environment

Environmental problems are indeed in the spotlight, environmental problems are often big problems. Social criticism related to the environment is an increasingly relevant topic in today's global context, especially due to the impact of global warming, climate change, ecosystem damage, and overexploitation of natural resources. In addition, the impact of industrial activities can also be one of the major environmental problems. Based on this, table 8 describes social criticism related to the environment in the novel *Majnun* by Anton Kurnia.

Table 8. Social Criticism of the Environment in the Novel *Majnun* by Anton Kurnia

Quotation	Criticized aspects	Data code
<i>"Global warming exacerbated by the impact of industry and the greed of capitalism could lead to disasters, including climate change and rising sea levels around the world as a result of melting snow and ice."</i>	Global warming	M/D24/L/p. 190
<i>"It is exacerbated by the problem of waste and plastic waste as an impact of industries that are very detrimental to environmental sustainability"</i>	Industry impact	M/D24/L/p. 190

Information: M: *Majnun*; D: *Data*; P: *Politics*; Pp: *Yard*

The results of research in the novel *Majnun* by Anton Kurnia include social criticism about the environment, namely about global warming and the impact of industrial activities. In daily life, there are activities that can cause global warming and the impact of industrial activities. This causes climate change, climate change makes natural ecosystems disrupted. The impact of industrial activities such as plastic waste or liquid waste can cause the balance of the ecosystem and nature preservation to be disturbed.

Social Criticism of Family Disorganization

The social problem of family disorganization is a problem that concerns everyone. This problem is related to the family, the problem can be caused by actions that hurt the family, family disorganization can occur due to the divorce of both parents, prolonged family conflicts, domestic violence (KDRT), and the lack

of parental roles. Family disorganization has a negative impact on victims or individuals. The impact provides bad footage that can be traumatizing for the victim. Based on this, table 9 describes the social criticism related to family disorganization in the novel *Majnun* by Anton Kurnia.

Table 9. Social Criticism of Family Disorganization in the Novel *Majnun* by Anton Kurnia

Quotation	Criticized aspects	Data code
"However, as a child, Zulaikha was often a victim of violence by her own mother. Her mother often vents her frustration due to fighting with her father to Zulaikha."	Verbal violence in children	M/D26/DK/p. 87
"When I was nine years old, my mother pinched my mouth to the point of bleeding and locked me in my room all day as punishment. My mistake is just asking"	Verbal violence in children	M/D27/DK/p. 95

Information: M: *Majnun*; D: Data; P: Politics; Pp: Yard

The results of the research in the novel *Majnun* by Anton Kurnia contain social problems related to family disorganization. This happens because of the disharmony in a family. This has been criticized for having a big negative impact on the victim. The relevance of life from social criticism of family disorganization is the existence of violence against children committed by parents. For example, parents who vent their frustrations to their children even though their children did nothing wrong. Such verbal violence is what traumatizes children. Factors that cause family disorganization include economic imbalances, violence and oppression. Parents who experience this problem will be depressed and vent their frustration to their children. This can have an impact on the development of individuals or victims, damage to family relationships and also have a negative impact on society.

Discussion

Breathe results that have been found by the author in the research activities of the social point in the novel *Majnun* Anton Kurnia's work there are social problems during the New Era. This problem is clearly illustrated in the novel *Majnun* by Anton Kurnia. In the novel, there are socio-political or government problems. In the novel, it raises the problem of government injustice, corruption cases and arbitrary actions of the rulers. In today's life there are many of the same problems, The relevance in today's life of political/government criticism is very clear, according to the novel that a high-ranking person or person with a higher position will use the position to act arbitrarily. In *Majnun*'s novel, there is a social criticism about the provision of wages that are not complete. In daily life, many government officials give incomplete wages to their workers, while the workers have given as much energy as possible. In the novel, it is explained that the rulers commit embezzlement or corruption, this is already seen as commonplace in Indonesia. Many state officials use state money for personal gain and legitimize all means to maintain their position in government. In addition to corruption, bribery activities are also rampant in Indonesia. Many people want a position by using money or bribes to be able to occupy that position. One of the reasons why money politics is rampant is when the role of political parties is dwarfed, so that the institution of political parties is weakened. Then the problem of the implementation of an open proportional system which has an impact on the weakening of party institutions then boils down to behavior *money politic* is closely related to this (Revan et al., 2022). In addition to political problems, there is also the problem of economic inequality that has a big impact on the community. Economic instability occurs because of economic practices. In today's life, one of these problems is the existence of economic inequality that is clearly visible. The lowly or the poor were considered slaves by the richer people. This happens a lot nowadays, rich people think that poor people are weak people and have nothing. In addition, many people carry out industrial exploitation actions, where companies or individuals take advantage of resources, labor and the surrounding environment. The socio-economic criticism in the novel discusses the economics of capitalism where humans are enslaved to carry out economic activities.

The problems that occurred at that time were also about morality, in the novel it discusses social and moral criticism. In accordance with the analysis carried out, the novel tells a character who is stubborn, arrogant, greedy, cruel and cunning. In daily life, many people are also arrogant about what they have, in addition to being arrogant, there is also human greed. Nowadays, many people are greedy to get as much luck as possible, it is this trait that the author criticizes. In addition, human nature is also cruel and cunning, people can commit cruelty to anyone if they don't get what they want from others. Nowadays, many people commit acts of cruelty to fellow human beings because the person is hurt. Nowadays there are also many people who are cunning towards their neighbors, they do not care about others and are only selfish.

In addition to these problems, there is a problem that is quite prominent, namely the problem of gender equality. In this novel, he criticizes the problem of gender inequality. Gender inequality can be in various fields or various aspects, for example in the fields of education, employment, injustice in the political and legal systems, health and reproductive rights issues and many others. In the novel *Majnun* by Anton Kurnia, it tells the story of gender inequality. This is very prominent, because women are considered to always be below men. In today's life, a woman must always be below men, but in reality a woman can also be equal and equal to men. Women are also considered to always be behind men, in daily life many women who can exceed men are considered incapable due to gender differences. Another social problem is related to culture, in the novel there is a social criticism of culture. This social criticism includes cultural practices, norms, and values that are considered problematic or unfair. In the novel, what becomes the permas of the social cultural allergy is the fading of traditional cultural values. Nowadays, many people have abandoned traditional culture that is believed for generations, this happens because of modernization. For example, the loss of traditional culture, namely traditional games, in ancient times traditional games such as playing congkak, gobak sodor and other toys became the daily activities of young children but now they have begun to fade and even disappeared because today's children tend to choose to play *smartphones* instead of playing traditional toys. Religion, as a system of beliefs and values, is often expected to be a moral guide for society. However, religion can also be a source of social problems or a target of social criticism. In this novel, criticizing religion, the problem is related to a person's disbelief in religion, the problem is criticized because the person is considered to have no belief in God. In the novel, there is a socio-religious criticism that discusses doubting religion. In daily life, many people also doubt religion, for whom religion is not very important. People who do not believe in religion usually have their own beliefs that are far different from the religious teachings that exist in Indonesia.

A person who believes in the existence of a religion will definitely have a high sense of humanity, in the novel *Majnun* also criticizes humanitarian problems. This social critique discusses about inequality of human rights (HAM), human dignity and human welfare, but in life it can be seen that there are many things that need to be criticized, for example on the gap or discrimination in an ethnicity, group or religion. In the novel *Majnun* criticizes about the existence of discrimination of an ethnicity. Discrimination or discrimination against a different ethnicity or group. Today, ethnic and religious discrimination is still common. In Indonesia, there is still clearly visible discriminatory behavior. Ethnic or ethnic discrimination is also very visible, for example, discrimination against Papuans and other ethnic people who are considered different from others. This discrimination sometimes triggers disputes between human groups. In addition, religious discrimination also occurs because other religious minorities are small so that they are considered to be different small groups. Even though in reality it will not differentiate between one and the other. Another problem is about the environment, in this novel also criticizes environmental problems. Social criticism of the environment occurs due to a surge in population, air and water pollution due to waste, deforestation and burning of forests for land clearing, agriculture, fisheries, mining, and unsustainable development, a consumerist lifestyle, and the birth of large corporations that exploit natural resources are some of the human activities that cause environmental damage (Laksonia & Wijaksono, 2022). Social criticism related to the environment is an increasingly relevant topic in today's global context, especially due to the impact of global warming, climate change, ecosystem damage, and overexploitation of natural resources. In addition, the impact of

industrial activities can also be one of the major environmental problems. In Majnun's novel There is a social criticism about the environment, namely about global warming and the impact of industrial activities. In daily life, there are activities that can cause global warming and the impact of industrial activities. This causes climate change, climate change makes natural ecosystems disrupted. The impact of industrial activities such as plastic waste or liquid waste can cause the balance of the ecosystem and nature preservation to be disturbed. The last social problem found in this novel is related to the problem of family disorganization. This problem is related to the family, the problem can be caused by actions that hurt the family, family disorganization can occur due to the divorce of both parents, prolonged family conflicts, domestic violence (KDRT), and the lack of parental roles. Family disorganization has a negative impact on victims or individuals. The impact provides bad footage that can be traumatizing for the victim. Family disorganization is the division of the family as a unit because its members fail to fulfill their obligations in accordance with their social roles (Mustafidah et al., 2022). In Majnun's novel, data is found that it occurred Family disorganization in the characters in the novel, this happens because of disharmony in a family. This has been criticized because it has a great negative impact on the victim. In today's life, many acts of family disorganization are violence against children committed by parents. For example, parents who vent their frustrations to their children even though their children did nothing wrong. Such verbal violence is what traumatizes children. Factors that cause family disorganization include economic imbalances, violence and oppression. Parents who experience this problem will be depressed and vent their frustration to their children. This can have an impact on the development of individuals or victims, damage to family relationships and also have a bad impact on society.

Conclusion

Based on the analysis of social criticism in the novel *Majnun* by Anton Kurnia that has been carried out by the author, it can be concluded that in the novel *Majnun* by Anton Kurnia there is social criticism that can be analyzed, the social criticism includes 9 (nine) aspects, namely socio-political/government criticism, economy, moral, gender, culture, religion, humanity, environment and family disorganization. The novel provides an overview or reflection of the social situation at that time, there were many social events that could be criticized. In the novel *Majnun* by Anton Kurnia, it highlights many things that are relevant to today's life. In addition, the themes raised in *Majnun* are still very relevant to the conditions of society today. Relevant things such as bribery and embezzlement are still there, the economic gap in Indonesia is still very high, human morals and behavior at will, the underdevelopment of women who are considered weak by men, the fading of traditional culture, a person's distrust of religion, the existence of ethnic and religious discrimination in Indonesia, environmental damage caused by global warming and industrial activities and the amount of violence against children who are caused by parental pressure.

Through this study, social criticism in the novel *Majnun* by Anton Kurnia has significant implications in daily life. Social criticism not only serves as a reflection on injustice and inequality in society, but can also influence the way we think, act, and interact in social contexts. Through this social critique, it provides an increase in social awareness, builds social solidarity and provides awareness of gender equality. In this study, there are limitations beyond the control of the researcher, either directly or indirectly, so that it affects the results of the research. Many social criticisms can be included in more than one classification. This may be different from the person who read the results of this study. The researcher suggests that people who will research further to be able to read carefully, in the classification of social problems is also done carefully and better understood. By doing a deeper understanding, you will get more complete research results.

Acknowledgement

We would like to thank the Universitas Muhammadiyah Purwokerto for fully supporting this research.

Conflict of Interests

The author states no conflict of interest.

Reference

- Agustianto, R. (2017). *Super Accurate Sociology*. Bhuana Popular Science.
- Ahmad, K., Review, F., & Sastra, S. (2024). *Social Criticism In The Novel Anak Rantau*. 7(2).
- Alsyrad, R., & Rosa, H. T. (2020). Social Criticism in the Short Story of the Sky Getting Cloudy by Kipanjikusmin: A Review of Literary Sociology. *Arkhaiis*, 11(1), 15.
- Arum, D. Sekar, Amalia, L. R., & Putri, W. R. (2024). Social Criticism in the Novel Burung Kayu by Niduparas Erlang (A Review of Literary Sociology). *KABASTRA: Language and Literature Studies*, 3(2), 373–387. <https://doi.org/10.31002/kabastra.v3i2.1230>
- Dewi, W. O. S., & Balawa, L. O. (2017). Social Criticism in the Novel Surat Cinta para Kisha by Bintang Berkisah. *Bastra Journal*, 1(4), 1–13.
- Febrilian, R. N. A., Fathurohman, I., & Ahsin, M. N. (2022). The representation of social criticism in the novel Feeling Smart and Stupid does not have Rusdi Mathari's work. *Education: Journal of Educational Innovation*, 1(4), 183–191. <https://doi.org/10.56916/ejip.v1i4.187>
- Hasibuan, H. N. H., Effendi, A., & Margana, M. (2021). Social Criticism in Conspiracy of the Novel Universe by Fiersa Besari. *Sociohumanities*, 23(2), 218. <https://doi.org/10.24198/sosiohumaniora.v23i2.32132>
- Hieu, H. N. (2021). Social Criticism in their short story spells the prohibition of begging by Ahmad Tohari (Literary Sociology Study). *KREDO : Scientific Journal of Language and Literature*, 5(1), 175–191. <https://doi.org/10.24176/kredo.v5i1.6138>
- Humaira, A. N. A., & Satriani, I. (2024). Reflections of Society in the Short Story When All Beautiful Women by Tere Liye: A Sociological Study of Literature by Ian Watt. *Variable Research Journal*, 1(2), 325–330.
- Judace, A. (2011). *Community Organizing and Development*. Humanities.
- I.M.S. Widyantara, I.W. Rasna, & I.P.M. Dewantara. (2022). Social Criticism in a Short Story Collection of Old Shoes by Sapardi Djoko Damono. *Journal of Education and Learning Indonesian*, 11(2), 118–125. https://doi.org/10.23887/jurnal_bahasa.v11i2.978
- Laksonia, R. R., & Wijaksono, D. S. (2022). Representation of Social Criticism of Environmental Damage in Hayao Miyazaki's Animated Film Princess Mononoke. *Journal of Language, Literature and Teaching Studies (KIBASP)*, 6(1), 215–228. <https://doi.org/10.31539/kibasp.v6i1.4520>
- Kurnia, A. (2022). *Majnun*. A light bulb.
- Luthfi, A. H. (2020). Semiotic Analysis of Social Criticism in Humor in Fact Comics. *Journal of Communication Sciences*, 17(1), 19–40. <https://doi.org/10.24002/jik.v17i1.1968>
- Magnis, F., & Suseno. (2016). *Karl Marx's Thought: From Utopian Socialism to Revisionist Dispute*. PT. Gramedia Pustaka Utama.
- Mahmoodi, M. (2017). Social Criticism on Works of Contemporary Women Story Writers. *Advances in Language and Literary Studies*, 8(4), 50. <https://doi.org/10.7575/aiac.all.v.8n.4p.50>
- Maryati, K., & Suryawati, J. (2016). *Sociology for High School and MA ketsp Content Standards 2006*. Publisher Erlangga.
- Masrizal. (2015). *Control of Social Problems through Local Wisdom*. Syiah Kuala University Press Darusaalam.

- Mustafidah, D., Nurmalisa, D., & Pekalongan, U. (2022). *Social criticism in the framework of magical realism in the beautiful novel is a wound by Eka Kurniawan*. 4(2), 74–89.
- Navira Surya Andani, Resdianto Permata Raharjo, & Titik Indarti. (2022). Social Criticism and Individual Moral Values of the Main Character in the Novel *Laut Bercerita* by Leila S. Chudori. *HORN: Journal of Education, Language, Literature, Arts, and Culture*, 3(1), 21–32. <https://doi.org/10.37304/enggang.v3i1.7832>
- Novitasari, L. (2021). Social Criticism in the Novel *Pasung Jiwa* by Okky Madasari. *Indonesian Language Education and Literature*, 6(2), 321. <https://doi.org/10.24235/ileal.v6i2.6560>
- Pratiwi, Y. I., Harun, M., & R, H. (2018). Social Criticism in the Novel *Tanah Paradise Merah* by Arafat Nur. *JIM PBSI: Student Scientific Journal*, 3(3), 281–293.
- Primasanti, M. A. N., & Alrianingrum, S. (2017). Socio-Political Criticism of Iwan Fals' Songs in the New Order Period. *Avatara - e-Journal of History Education*, 5(3), 766–780.
- Revan, M., Makarim, F., & Fahmi, K. (2022). Journal of Social and Policy Issues Problems and Impacts of the Implementation of the Open Proportional Election System on the Political System. *Journal of Social and Policy Issues*, 2(2).
- Ricoeur, P. (1981). *The Rule of Metaphor: Multi-disciplinary Studies of the Creation of Meaning in Language*. University of Toronto Press.
- Safitry, R., & Tjahjono, T. (2023). Social Criticism in the Novel *Re and Perempuan* by Maman Suherman (Sociology of Literature of Gillin and Gillin). *Bapala*, 10(2), 48–59.
- Sapitri, P., & Tarmini, W. (2023). Social Criticism Through the Elements of Stile in the Novel *Majnun* by Anton Kurnia. *Hortatori: Journal of Indonesian Language and Literature Education*, 7(2), 141–149. <https://doi.org/10.30998/jh.v7i2.1947>
- Satriati, W., & Hapsarani, D. (2020). Social Criticism in Okky Madasari's Children Novel. *Proceeding of the International University Symposium on Humanities and Arts 2020*, 593(Inusharts 2020), 326–332.
- Siti, N., & Zahra, A. (2022). *Social Criticism in Tere Liye's Goodbye Novel: A Sociological Review of Literature and Its Implications in Language Learning* https://repository.unsri.ac.id/75983/%0Ahttps://repository.unsri.ac.id/75983/3/RAMA_88201_0602_1181823014_0006125201_01_front_ref.pdf
- Soerjano, S. (2006). *Sociology of an Introduction*. Raja Grafindo Persada.
- Solihat, I. (2017). Literary Sociology of Mirror Manuscripts (Conflict, Social Criticism, Moral Values). *Journal of Reading*, 2, 29–36.
- Stark, A., & Huszka, B. (2022). 100 Years Sitti Nurbaya: A View on the Social Criticism in the Novel *Sitti Nurbaya*. *Asian Culture and History*, 14(1), 67. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ach.v14n1p67>
- Sukma Aji, M., & Arifin, Z. (2022). Social Criticism in the Novel *Orang Oetimu* by Felix K. Nesi and its Relevance as Teaching Material in High School: A Review of Literary Sociology. *HORN: Journal of Education, Language, Literature, Arts, and Culture*, 2(2), 72–82. <https://doi.org/10.37304/enggang.v2i2.3885>
- Susanto, E. (2016). *Hermeneutics Studies*. PT. Fajar Interpretama Mandiri.
- Susiati, S., Nacikit, J., & Yusdianti Tenriawali, A. (2022). Social Criticism in Novel's *Broken Wings* by Kahlil Gibran. *Language and Literature*, 7(2), 69–80.
- Thorina, J., & Azeharie, S. (2023). Representation of Social Criticism in the Film 'The White Tiger' (Semiotic Analysis of Roland Barthes). *Connection*, 7(2), 365–374. <https://doi.org/10.24912/kn.v7i2.21393>
- Tutesa, & Wisman, Y. (2020). Social Problems in Society. *Journal of Social Science Education (JPIPS)*, 12(2), 94–99.
- Wajdi, M., Hadi Purnomo, S., Mariam, S., Negeri Bali, P., & Negeri Malang, P. (2024). Exploration of

dynamics of social class in the Indonesian novel “Laskar Pelangi.” *Journal of Education, Social, and Communication Studies*, 1(1), 35–45.

Wulandari, S. R., & Hayati, Y. (2023). Social Criticism in the Novel Komsa Komsa by E.S ITO: A Study of Literary Sociology. *Journal of Genres (Language, Literature, and Learning)*, 5(1), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.26555/jg.v5i1.7555>

